

“Assess The Level Of Self -Esteem Among B.Sc. Nursing 1st Year Students In Selected Nursing Colleges Of Jabalpur City With The View To Develop self -Esteem Awareness Booklet”

POONAM MALVIYA¹, MANJU KALVIN²

¹MASTER OF SCIENCE IN NURSING, ²PROFESOR

^{1,2}MENTAL HEALTH NURSING DEPARTMENT

^{1,2}GOVERNMENT NURSING COLLEGE N.S.C.B.
JABALPUR (M.P)

ABSTRACT: This study aimed to assess the level of self-esteem among first-year B.Sc. Nursing students in selected nursing colleges in Jabalpur City, with the goal of developing a self-esteem awareness booklet. A descriptive quantitative research design was employed, utilizing a self-administered questionnaire to collect data on socio-demographic variables and self-esteem levels, measured using the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale. A sample of 100 students was selected using purposive sampling. Results showed that 74% of students had medium self-esteem, 22% had low self-esteem, and 4% had high self-esteem. No significant association was found between self-esteem levels and socio-demographic factors, including age, family type, marital status, parental education, occupation, and other factors. The findings suggest that self-esteem levels among B.Sc. Nursing students are generally medium, with no significant socio-demographic predictors. The study emphasizes the need for interventions to enhance self-esteem, with a focus on cultural and socio-economic factors, and recommends further research on influencing factors and effective interventions.

KEYWORDS: *Self-esteem, B.Sc. Nursing, first-year students, socio-demographic variables, self-awareness booklet, Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale.*

INTRODUCTION : You may be the only person left who believes in you, but it's enough. It takes just one star to pierce a universe of darkness. -Richelle E Goodrich Self-esteem is your subjective sense of overall personal worth or value. Similar to self-respect, it describes your level of confidence in your abilities and attributes. Having healthy self-esteem can influence your motivation, your mental well-being, and your overall quality of life. However, having self-esteem that is either too high or too low can be problematic. Better understanding what your unique level of self-esteem is help you strike a balance that is just right for you.

NEED FOR THE STUDY - Self-esteem appears vital to our mental and physical wellbeing. Research has confirmed that it improves performance in particular domains, such as in education and more generally, positively impacts our physical and psychological health and social acceptance (Jordan et al 2017).

OBJECTIVES

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- Assess the level of knowledge regarding self-esteem among B.Sc. Nursing 1st year

students in selected nursing colleges of Jabalpur city.

- Develop self-esteem awareness among B.Sc. Nursing 1st year students through selfawareness booklet.

- Find association between self-esteem among b.sc nursing 1st year students with

selected socio demographic variables.

Research Methodology

Nursing students- an individual who is enrolled in a professional nursing educational

program.

ASSUMPTIONS

The researcher Assumes that-

- The students must have little knowledge about Self -esteem.
- Level of knowledge regarding self -esteem differs from individual to individual.

LIMITATIONS

- Time and cost constraint is the limitation of the present study.
- Small sample size will be the limitation of the study.
- Data collection method is limited with the tool which is prepared by the

researcher

DELIMITATIONS

- B.Sc. Nursing 1st year students.
- Students who are study in only nursing college of Jabalpur.

RESEARCH APPROACH The research approach is the most essential part of any research. The selection of research approach is the basic procedure for the conduct of research enquiry. A research approach tells the researcher what data to collect and how to analyze it. It also suggests possible conclusions to be drawn from the data. In view of the nature of the problem selected and to accomplish the objectives of the study, a Quantitative research approach was considered as best suited to assess the level of self -esteem among B.Sc. nursing 1st year students in selected nursing colleges of Jabalpur city with the view to develop self -esteem awareness booklet". Polit and Hungler explained that the classical approach for conducting research consists of four phases namely; ▪ Determining the objectives of the programme ▪ Developing means for measuring the attainment of those objectives ▪ Collecting data ▪ Interpreting the data Therefore, descriptive survey approach was found to be appropriate for the present study. The entire study is based on it the research approach was selected as quantitative approach. For the present study Quantitative Research Approach was applied

RESEARCH DESIGN :Research design is a blueprint of a scientific study. It helps to identify and address the problem that may rise during the process of research and analysis. In the present study descriptive research design was used. Descriptive research design is a type of research design that aims to

systematically obtain information to describe a phenomenon, situation, or population.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY: Burns N, Grove S interpreted that the population referred to as the target population which represents the entire group or all the elements like individuals or objects that meet certain standards for inclusion in the study. In the present study, the population comprises of the nursing students who are studying in nursing colleges of Jabalpur. • Target population – B.Sc. Nursing 1st year students who are studying in selected college of Jabalpur city are target population. • Accessible population - B.Sc. Nursing 1ST year student who are fulfilling the inclusion criteria will be the accessible population

SAMPLE SIZE: Sample size of 100 nursing students were selected based on the inclusion criteria of the study. **SAMPLE TECHNIQUES:** Grove SK defined that, sampling is the process of selecting a group of people or other elements with which to conduct a study. He also explained that the purposive sampling involves the selection of subjects which are available at the right place in the right time. The samples for the present study were taken from selected nursing college of Jabalpur by using purposive sampling technique.

DEPENDENT VARIABLES: The dependent variables will be level of knowledge regarding self -esteem among B.Sc. nursing students. **DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES-** The demographic variables were as age, type of family, marital status, educational status of mother and father, occupational status of mother and father, monthly income, language issues, previous knowledge, source of previous knowledge, communication problem, stay, residential area, extra-curricular activities

A quantitative research approach, descriptive research design used to conduct the study among B.Sc. nursing 1st-year students using a self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire collected data on socio-demographic variables such as age, type of family, marital status, educational status of parents, occupation of parents, monthly income, language-related issues, previous knowledge, source of knowledge, communication problems, place of stay, and participation in extracurricular activities. A sample of 100 B.Sc. nursing first year students from a selected using purposive sampling method. The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale was used to measure the level of self-esteem among students. Data were analysed using chi-

square tests to assess the association between socio-demographic variables and self-esteem.

TOOL

THE TOOL CONSISTS OF SECTION A & SECTION B

SECTION A: SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

It includes socio demographic details such as age, marital status, educational status of mother and father, type of family, family income, occupational status of mother and father, communication problem, source of information, extracurricular activities, stay, residential area, language issues, previous knowledge.

SECTION B: STANDARDIZED TOOL Rosenberg Self -esteem self-report Scale (RSE) will be used to measure self -esteem of B.Sc. nursing students. The Rosenberg Self -esteem Scale, a widely used self-report instrument for evaluating individual self -esteem, was investigated using item response theory. Factor analysis identified a single common factor, contrary to some previous studies that extracted separate Self-Confidence and Self-Depreciation factors. A unidimensional model for graded item responses was fit to the data. A model that constrained the 10 items to equal discrimination was contrasted with a model allowing the discriminations to be estimated freely. The test of significance indicated that the unconstrained model better fit the data-that is, the 10 items of the Rosenberg Self - esteem Scale are not equally discriminating and are differentially related to self -esteem. The pattern of functioning of the items was examined with respect to their content, and observations are offered with implications for validating and developing future personality instruments.

RELIABILITY: The scale generally has high reliability. The test-retest correlations are typically in the range of .82 to .88, and Cronbach's alpha for various samples are in the range of .77 to .88. Studies have demonstrated both a unidimensional and a two-factor (self-confidence and self-deprecation) structure to the scale. Instructions for the Administration of the test: The scale consists of ten statements that you could possibly apply to yourself. You must rate on how much you agree with each. The items should be answered quickly without over thinking, your first inclination is what you should put down.

Results

PRESENTATION OF DATA All the item in the tool where codes and transferred to a master sheet for computer programming for statistical analysis investigators and inferential statistics.

SECTION 1- Descriptive of sample characteristics frequency and percentages were computed describing the sample characteristics.

SECTION 2- Descriptive of students' self -esteem of B.sc nursing 1st year students and percentage were computed for description of level of self -esteem.

SECTION 3- Association between students' level of self -esteem with selected demographic variables.

Table – 4.1
Frequency and percentage Distribution of students according to socio-Demographic variable

Demographic Variables	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Age of The Students	18-20 years	62	62.0	62.0	62.0
	21-22 years	23	23.0	23.0	85.0
	23-24 Years	10	10.0	10.0	95.0
	above 24 years	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	
Type of Family	Nuclear Family	14	14.0	14.0	14.0
	Joint Family	62	62.0	62.0	76.0
	Single Parent	19	19.0	19.0	95.0
	Extended Family	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	
Marital Status of Students.	Married	24	24.0	24.0	24.0
	Unmarried	76	76.0	76.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	
Educational Status of The Mother	Middle School	31	31.0	31.0	31.0
	High School	28	28.0	28.0	59.0
	Higher Secondary	32	32.0	32.0	91.0
	Graduate	9	9.0	9.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	
Educational Status of The Father	Middle School	3	3.0	3.0	3.0
	High School	37	37.0	37.0	40.0
	Higher Secondary	9	9.0	9.0	49.0
	Graduate	51	51.0	51.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	
Occupation of Mother	House Wife	73	73.0	73.0	73.0
	Business	13	13.0	13.0	86.0
	Job-Worker	14	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.1

Frequency And Percentage Distribution of The Respondents According to Their

Age

Demographic Variables		Frequency	Percent
Age of The Students	18-20 years	62	62%
	21-22 years	23	23%
	23-24 Years	10	10%
	above 24 years	5	5%
	Total	100	100%

Fig. No. 4.1.1 Diagram Representing The Percentage of Self-Esteem According To Age

Table 4.2

Frequency And Percentage Distribution of Level of Self-Esteem of the Students

Level of Self-esteem	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Low Self-esteem	22	22.0	22.0	22.0
Medium Self-esteem	74	74.0	74.0	96.0
High Self-esteem	4	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Fig no. 4.1.16 Diagram Representing the level of self- esteem of the Respondent

Table 4.1.16 represents the level of self -esteem of the students. The table shows the frequency and percentage of respondents belonging to each level of self -esteem, as well as the valid and cumulative percentage. The table shows that the majority of students (74%) have medium self -esteem, while only a small percentage (4%) have high self -esteem. 22% of students have low self - esteem. The cumulative percentage indicates that 96% of students have medium self-esteem, 22% of students have low self -esteem while only 4% of student high self – esteem

Association between Demographic Variables and Level of Self-Esteem

1. Age of the Students

- **18-20 years:** Low (14), Medium (45), High (3) - Total: 62
- **21-22 years:** Low (6), Medium (17), High (0) - Total: 23
- **23-24 years:** Low (0), Medium (9), High (1) - Total: 10
- **Above 24 years:** Low (2), Medium (3), High (0) - Total: 5

○ Chi-value: 5.745, df: 6, p-value: 0.452

2. Type of Family

- **Nuclear Family:** Low (4), Medium (8), High (2) - Total: 14
- **Joint Family:** Low (14), Medium (46), High (2) - Total: 62
- **Single Parent:** Low (3), Medium (16), High (0) - Total: 19
- **Extended Family:** Low (1), Medium (4), High (0) - Total: 5

○ Chi-value: 6.212, df: 6, p-value: 0.400

3. Marital Status

- **Married:** Low (5), Medium (19), High (0) - Total: 24
- **Unmarried:** Low (17), Medium (55), High (4) - Total: 76
 - **Chi-value:** 1.397, **df:** 2, **p-value:** 0.497

4. Educational Status of the Mother

- **Middle School:** Low (8), Medium (20), High (3) - Total: 31
- **High School:** Low (5), Medium (23), High (0) - Total: 28
- **Higher Secondary:** Low (7), Medium (25), High (0) - Total: 32
- **Graduate:** Low (2), Medium (6), High (1) - Total: 9
 - **Chi-value:** 7.226, **df:** 6, **p-value:** 0.300

5. Educational Status of the Father

- **Middle School:** Low (0), Medium (3), High (0) - Total: 3
- **High School:** Low (9), Medium (26), High (2) - Total: 37
- **Higher Secondary:** Low (2), Medium (7), High (0) - Total: 9
- **Graduate:** Low (11), Medium (38), High (2) - Total: 51
 - **Chi-value:** 1.782, **df:** 6, **p-value:** 0.939

6. Occupation of the Mother

- **Housewife:** Low (15), Medium (54), High (4) - Total: 73
- **Business:** Low (4), Medium (9), High (0) - Total: 13
- **Job Worker:** Low (3), Medium (11), High (0) - Total: 14
 - **Chi-value:** 2.085, **df:** 4, **p-value:** 0.720

7. Occupation of the Father

- **Job Worker:** Low (9), Medium (36), High (2) - Total: 47
- **Business:** Low (4), Medium (9), High (0) - Total: 13
- **Jobless:** Low (1), Medium (3), High (0) - Total: 4
- **Other:** Low (8), Medium (26), High (2) - Total: 36
 - **Chi-value:** 1.649, **df:** 6, **p-value:** 0.949

8. Monthly Income of Family

- **Below 10000:** Low (9), Medium (32), High (0) - Total: 41
- **10000-20000:** Low (7), Medium (19), High (2) - Total: 28
- **20000-50000:** Low (6), Medium (23), High (2) - Total: 31
 - **Chi-value:** 3.244, **df:** 4, **p-value:** 0.518

9. Language Related Issue

- **Hindi:** Low (7), Medium (25), High (0) - Total: 32
- **English:** Low (14), Medium (39), High (4) - Total: 57
- **Other:** Low (1), Medium (10), High (0) - Total: 11
 - **Chi-value:** 4.759, **df:** 4, **p-value:** 0.313

10. Previous Knowledge

- **Yes:** Low (17), Medium (43), High (3) - Total: 63

- **No:** Low (5), Medium (31), High (1) - Total: 37
 - **Chi-value:** 2.929, **df:** 2, **p-value:** 0.231

11. Source of Knowledge

- **Multimedia:** Low (6), Medium (15), High (1) - Total: 22
- **Newspaper:** Low (2), Medium (2), High (0) - Total: 4
- **Other:** Low (7), Medium (19), High (2) - Total: 28
- **No:** Low (7), Medium (38), High (1) - Total: 46
 - **Chi-value:** 5.047, **df:** 6, **p-value:** 0.538

12. Communication Problem

- **Level 1:** Low (1), Medium (17), High (1) - Total: 21
- **Level 2:** Low (19), Medium (56), High (3) - Total: 78
 - **Chi-value:** 1.340, **df:** 4, **p-value:** 0.855

13. Stay

- **Hostel:** Low (7), Medium (27), High (3) - Total: 37
- **Rented House:** Low (11), Medium (34), High (0) - Total: 45
- **Home:** Low (4), Medium (13), High (1) - Total: 18
 - **Chi-value:** 3.780, **df:** 4, **p-value:** 0.437

14. Participation in Extra-Curricular Activities

- **Yes:** Low (16), Medium (52), High (3) - Total: 71
- **No:** Low (6), Medium (22), High (1) - Total: 29
 - **Chi-value:** 0.082, **df:** 2, **p-value:** 0.960

15. Residence

- **Rural:** Low (10), Medium (19), High (2) - Total: 31
- **Urban:** Low (12), Medium (55), High (2) - Total: 69
 - **Chi-value:** 3.805, **df:** 2, **p-value:** 0.149

The analysis indicates no significant association between the demographic variables and levels of self-esteem, as evidenced by p-values greater than 0.05 across all categories.

Major findings Age Distribution: The majority of the respondents (62%) were between 18 and 20 years old, followed by 23% between 21 and 22 years old, 10% between 23 and 24 years old, and only 5% were over 24 years old. Type of Family: The majority of the respondents (62%) came from joint families, followed by single-parent families (19%) and nuclear families (14%). Only 5% of the respondents came from extended families. Marital Status: The majority of the respondents (76%) were unmarried, while 24% were married. Educational Status of the mother: The highest proportion of mothers (32%) had a higher secondary education, followed by middle school (31%) and high school (28%). Only 9% of the mothers were graduates. Educational Status of the Father: The majority of the fathers (51%) were graduates, followed by high school graduates (37%). Only 9% of the fathers had a higher secondary education, and a small proportion (3%) completed middle school. Occupation of the mother: The majority of the mothers (73%) were housewives,

while 14% were job-workers and 13% were involved in some form of business.

Occupation of the Father: The majority of the fathers (47%) were job-workers, followed by those in other occupations (36%), involved in some form of business (13%), and those who were jobless (4%).

Monthly Income of the Family: The highest percentage of families (41%) had a monthly income below 10,000, followed by 28% with an income between 10,000 and 20,000, and 31% with an income between 20,000 and 50,000. Language Related Issue: The majority of the respondents (57%) were comfortable with English, followed by Hindi (32%) and other languages (11%). Previous Knowledge: 63% of the respondents had some prior knowledge of the topic, while 37% had no knowledge. Source of Knowledge: Only 22% of the respondents obtained information through multimedia sources, while 28% obtained information through other sources. A majority (46%) did not have any source of knowledge, and 4% obtained information through newspapers

Communication Problem: 22% of the respondents reported having communication problems, while 78% did not have any communication problems. Place of Stay: 37% of the respondents stayed in hostels, 45% in rented houses, and 18% in their own homes. Participation in Extra-Curricular Activities: 71% of the respondents had participated in extra-curricular activities, while 29% had not. Residence: 69% of the respondents lived in urban areas, while 31% lived in rural areas. Level of Self -esteem: The majority of students (74%) had medium self -esteem, while 22% had low self -esteem and only 4% had high self -esteem. Based on the data chi-square values reported along with their degrees of freedom and p-values for each variable. Overall, based on the given data and analysis showed that there is no significant association between any of the variables and level of self -esteem. Detailed interpretation are given under:

Age of the students: The chi-square value is 5.745 with 6 degrees of freedom and a pvalue of 0.452376. This suggests that there is no significant association between the age of the students and the demographic profile. Type of Family: The chi-square value is 6.212 with 6 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.399845. This suggests that there is no significant association between the type of family and the demographic profile.

Marital Status of Students: The chi-square value is 1.397 with 2 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.497427. This suggests that there is no significant association between the marital status of students and the demographic profile. Educational status of the mother: The chi-square value is 7.226 with 6 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.300492. This suggests that there is no significant association between the educational status of the mother and the demographic profile. Educational status of the father: The chi-square value is 1.782 with 6 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.938648. This suggests that there is no significant association between the educational status of the father and the demographic profile. Occupation of Mother: The chi-square value is 2.085 with 4 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.720055. This suggests that there is no significant association between the occupation of the mother and the demographic profile. Occupation of Father: The chi-square value is 1.649 with 6 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.948965. This suggests that there is no significant association between the occupation of the father and the demographic profile

Monthly income of family: The chi-square value is 3.244 with 4 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.517825. This suggests that there is no significant association between the monthly income of the family and the demographic profile. Language-related issue: The chi-square value is 4.759 with 4 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.312896. This suggests that there is no significant association between the language-related issue and the demographic profile. Previous knowledge: The chi-square value is 2.929 with 2 degrees of freedom and a pvalue of 0.231144. This suggests that there is no significant association between previous knowledge and the demographic profile. Source of Knowledge: The chi-square value is 5.047 with 6 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.537846. This suggests that there is no significant association between the source of knowledge and the demographic profile. Communication Problem: The chi-square value is 1.340 with 4 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.854517. This suggests that there is no significant association between communication problem and the demographic profile

Stay: The chi-square value is 3.780 with 4 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.436608. This suggests that there is no significant association between stay and the demographic profile. Participation in Ex-Curricular: The chi-square value is 0.082 with 2 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.959782. This

suggests that there is no significant association between participation in extracurricular activities and the demographic profile.

The majority of the students had medium self-esteem (74%), while 22% had low self-esteem, and only 4% had high self-esteem. The analysis revealed no significant association between any of the socio-demographic variables and the level of self-esteem among B.Sc. nursing 1st-year students. Factors such as age, type of family, marital status, educational status of parents, occupation of parents, monthly income, language-related issues, previous knowledge, source of knowledge, communication problems, place of stay, and participation in extracurricular activities did not show a significant relationship with self-esteem.

Conclusion The study findings indicate that the majority of B.Sc. nursing 1st-year students have a medium level of self-esteem. No significant associations were found between self-esteem and the selected socio-demographic variables. However, it is important to acknowledge that self-esteem is a complex construct influenced by individual differences, life experiences, and cultural background. Based on the results, interventions should be developed to enhance self-esteem among students, considering socio-economic backgrounds and gender disparities. Further research is recommended to explore additional factors influencing self-esteem and to develop effective interventions to promote positive self-concept among students.

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